

nitrogen levels (Table 2). P and K were applied basally at 40 kg/ha. Twenty-day-old seedlings of each variety were planted in 3- × 3-m plots at 30- × 7.5-cm spacing in a randomized complete block design in 3 replications.

Planting date significantly affected yield (Table 2). Jul seeding produced a normal crop, Sep seeding experienced cold stress at production phase, and Nov seeding experienced cold stress at vegetative phase. KN-361-BKK-27-1, IR9202-25-3-3, IR9202-22-3-2, and IR9224-K1 were cold tolerant at vegetative and reproductive phases, but low tillering caused low yields. They were, however, judged to be promising parents for the cold tolerance breeding program. RPKN-2 and KULU were cold tolerant at vegetative phase but susceptible at reproductive phase. B2012C-KN-1-3-2-2, BG90-2, TOS 103, IR9202-36-3-2, B737F-KN-10-3-1-2, and IR8965-K1 were susceptible at both growth stages.

Response to N was highest for the Nov seeding and least for the Sep seeding (Table 2). Adding N for Sep plantings caused high sterility and depressed yield

Table 2. Effect of planting date and nitrogen application on performance of 12 entries in the advanced cold tolerance yield nursery, 1982 Badeggi, Nigeria.

Entry	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)			N response ^b (t/ha)	
	P ₁	P ₂	P ₃	P ₂	P ₃
RPKN-2	4.2 bcde	4.1 f	5.4 d	1.0**	1.1**
B2012C-KN-15-1-3-2-3	5.5 de	4.3 f	4.8 cd	-0.4	2.7**
KULU	3.3 abcd	2.1 ab	4.5 cd	1.2**	0.4
BG 90-2 ^c	6.4 e	3.9 ef	4.4 cd	1.2**	0.3
TOS 103 ^c	4.7 cde	2.9 bcd	4.0 cd	-0.6	1.9**
KN-361-BKK-27-1	3.8 abcd	4.4 f	3.8 bcd	-0.7*	1.8**
IR9202-36-3-2-2	3.7 abcd	2.8 bc	3.5 abc	1.4**	0.1
B737F-KN-10-3-1-2	6.5 e	3.7 def	3.4 abc	-0.3	0.6*
IR9202-25-1-3	1.8 ab	2.8 bc	3.2 abc	0.3	1.9**
IR9202-22-3-2	2.1 ab	3.2 cde	2.1 ab	-1.9**	0.0
IR8965-K1	2.6 abc	2.3 abc	2.0 a	-0.1	0.7*
IR9224-K1	1.4 a	1.7 a	1.7 a	-0.4	1.3**
Mean	3.8	3.2	3.6		

^aP₁ P₂ P₃ = Jul, Sep, and Nov plantings. Minimum temp (°C) during 5 months of crop growth were 23, 23, 23, 23, 19 for July; 23, 23, 19, 16, 12 for Sep; and 18, 16, 17, 20, 22 for Nov. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bDifference of mean of 80 and 120 kg N/ha, and no N; * and ** = significant at 5% and 1% levels. P₂ = Sep seeding, P₃ = Nov seeding. ^cPopular wet season varieties.

for KN-361-BKK-27-1, B2012C-KN-15-1-3-2-3, B737F-KN-10-3-1-2, IR9202-22-3-2, IR9224-K1, IR8965-K1, and TOS103, but improved yield significantly for RPKN-2 in both plantings.

The test on RPKN-2, B2012C-KN-15-1-3-2-3, KULU, and KN-361-BKK-27-1, the highest yielders, is being repeated in cold tolerance multilocal trials and on-farm minikit trials. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Tissue culture

Embryo grafting of rice varieties

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We used an embryo grafting technique – the embryo of one rice variety is transferred to the blank endosperm of another variety – to study the DNA:RNA interaction of grafted plants on plant characters, especially F₁ spikelet sterility.

Under a stereoscope, the embryo from a healthy, dehulled, surface-sterilized kernel was removed aseptically using forceps and a fine needle, and transferred to the embryo groove of another kernel from a different variety. During transfer, the endosperm was dipped either in sterile deionized water (SDW) or in a starch suspension prepared by crushing the endosperm of the recipient variety with SDW.

Success of embryo grafting combinations.

Varietal combination		Embryos (no.)		Mortality (%) of grafted seedlings in pot
Embryo donor	Endosperm	Total grafted	Mature ^a	
BR1	BR4	80	0	
BR4	BR1	80	0	
BR1	BR7	80	3	60
BR7	BR1	80	0	
BR4	BR9	80	10	50
BR9	BR4	80	6	45
BR1	BR9	72	0	
BR9	BR1	72	0	
BR3	BR7	60	2	50
BR7	BR3	60	3	60
BR9	Dharial	60	3	60
Dharial	BR9	60	0	
BR4	Kasra	60	0	
Kasra	BR4	60	0	
BR4	Madhumala	60	0	
Madhumala	BR4	60	0	
BR9	Kasra	60	0	
Kasra	BR9	60	0	
BR4	<i>S. coarctata</i>	40	0	
<i>S. coarctata</i>	BR4	40	0	
BR9	<i>S. coarctata</i>	40	0	
<i>S. coarctata</i>	BR9	40	0	

^aThose at 1-4 mo after harvest.

After transfer, separate grafted kernels were placed on each of the following sterile substrates to germinate and grow: moist filter paper, moist sand, a perforated moist filter paper platform in a test tube, and a petri dish or test tube containing water agar (DIFCO) at concentrations of 2.0, 1.5, 1.0, 0.75, and 0.5%. In the water agar, grafted kernels were planted with the embryo end facing the cap or lid. Kernels were incubated at 26 + 2°C for 3 wk. Drops of SDW were added when necessary. For growth comparison, intact kernels of the two varieties

and their detached embryos were also placed in the media with the grafted kernels. To determine the best embryo age for successful grafting, embryos aged 4, 7, 10, and 14 d after anthesis were transferred to the mature endosperm of different varieties. Experiments were in four replications.

Grafting was confirmed when the endosperm was exhausted and squeezed into a thin membrane. After 2 wk, the embryo and the endosperm were completely bound together. Grafted plants were transferred to sterile pots with nutrient

solutions and covered with polyethylene sheets.

Results show that grafting was successful for BR4 and BR9 combinations (see table). The best substrate for grafted plant establishment was the 0.75% water agar medium. Grafting was successful only with embryos of more than 10 days after anthesis. Plants from grafted embryos and plants grown from normal seed were phenotypically similar in plant height, tiller number, and grain type. However, maturity date of grafted plants was 10-15 d later. □

Callus induction and plant regeneration from embryo tissues of rice

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We successfully induced calli and regenerated whole plantlets by culturing embryo-tissue of cultivar Palman 579, indicating that embryo culture might be used to propagate rice cultivars.

About 160 embryo tissues were cultured for callus induction; 80% began to grow as a separate friable mass of calli. Embryos were isolated from dehusked seeds, washed with distilled water, sterilized in 0.1% HgCl₂ solution for 10 min,

and washed 6 times in sterile distilled water. Embryos were cultured on Mura-shige and Skoog's medium (MS) (1962) supplemented by different concentrations of 2,4-D (1, 2, and 4 mg/liter). pH of the medium was adjusted to 5.8 and cultures were incubated at 26 ± 2°C with a 16 h/8 light/dark photoperiod. The MS medium was supplemented with 3% sucrose + 2,4-D (2 mg/liter) + coconut water (15% vol/vol) + casein hydrolysate (500 mg/liter).

After 34 subcultures, callus pieces were transferred to the differentiating medium containing MS + 1% sucrose + IAA (2 mg/liter) + coconut water (15 vol/vol) + casein hydrolysate (500 mg/liter). When

small shoot buds emerged on the surface of the callus tissues, 20% of the calli were separated into plantlets. Albino plants were occasionally found in the callus tissues.

Eighteen plantlets lived. They were transferred to MS basal medium with half the concentration of growth substances and then to a hormone-free basal medium to establish a vigorous root system. When plantlets grew 10-15 cm tall they were acclimatized in a growth chamber before transfer to the field. Albino plantlets died.

Meiotic analysis of the regenerated plants indicated a normal haploid chromosome number (n = 12). □

Pest management and control DISEASES

Control of black rot disease of azolla

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Black rot disease caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn is a serious disease of azolla. The pathogen first affects the middle portion of the azolla frond, then spreads gradually to the branches. Fronds rot and turn black in patches. We evaluated various fungicides for control of *R. solani* in in vitro laboratory tests. Carbendazim (2 - methoxy - carbamoyl benzimidazole) effectively inhibited *R. solani*. In a

later study, carbendazim was tested for *R. solani* control in 5-litre mud pots. Four litres of water, 5 ppm superphosphate, and 20 ppm carbofuran were added. Carbendazim levels of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 ppm were added to the pots. Azolla was inoculated at 15 g/pot. Azolla fresh weight was recorded 10 d later (see table).

When azolla was grown in mud pots, disease incidence substantially reduced azolla growth (see table). As carbendazim was increased, azolla growth also increased. Carbendazim at 50 ppm concentration gave maximum azolla growth.

Costs of using carbendazim are small (see table). A disease incidence is severe only in nursery plots where azolla growth

is abundant. Using the fungicides in nurseries may save azolla for field inoculation. □

Control of black rot disease of azolla, Tamil Nadu, India.

Carbendazim (ppm)	Mean azolla (g/pot)	% increase over control	Cost of carbendazim (\$/ha)
Control	8.33	—	—
10	16.67	100.12	0.19
20	19.00	128.09	0.38
30	19.17	130.13	0.57
40	19.83	138.06	0.75
50	20.67	148.14	0.94

CD: 1.0975